

CRIME PREVENTION MEASURES AND RESPONSE TO COMMUNITY SAFETY OF LOCAL RESIDENTS: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF PERCEPTION OF POLICE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 6

Pages: 697-708

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2091

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12803074

Manuscript Accepted: 06-27-2024

Crime Prevention Measures and Response to Community Safety of Local Residents: The Mediating Role of Perception of Police

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Abstract

This study in Kidapawan City explored how the perception of police mediates the relationship between crime prevention and community safety. It adapted a descriptive-correlation methodology, surveying 382 respondents from various local residents of Kidapawan City through face-to-face surveys. The study used Mean, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, Medgraph using the Sobel z-test, Regressions, and Mediation Test Technique. The findings reveal that study participants reported a high level of engagement in crime prevention activities and generally held a high sense of community safety, alongside a high level of perception of police. The analysis unveiled significant relationships among crime prevention, community safety, and perception of police. Notably, it revealed that while crime prevention has a direct effect on community safety, a significant portion of its influence operates indirectly through its impact on the perception of police. The immediate impact was statistically significant when mediated by the perception of police. In the mediation analysis, although the partial mediation regression coefficient significantly decreased, it remained significant in the final stage. These findings indicate that while the perception of police mediates some of the impact of crime prevention on community safety, other portions are either direct or mediated by other variables outside the model's scope. This suggests important implications for policy and practice, highlighting the critical role of police perception in enhancing community safety through crime prevention efforts. By understanding and improving community perceptions of police (MV), stakeholders can bolster the overall effectiveness of crime prevention(IV) strategies and foster a safer community environment.

Keywords: *criminal justice education, community, crime prevention, community safety, perception of police*

Introduction

Violence and crime have been identified as significant issues in the Philippines. According to statistics on crime volume, 374,277 crimes were reported in the Philippines in 2020 alone, and 360, 573 crimes were committed in all in 2021 (did.pnp, Christmastimes, 2022). This crime data indicates that the police response to community safety may be inadequate. In addition, studies have suggested that factors such as poverty, inequality, racial tension and prejudice, psychological problems, and gender discrimination contribute to crime and violence (De Wet, N., Somefun, O., & Rambau, N. 2018). Community members emphasize the importance of police legitimacy. Therefore, police officers must work to the full extent to be objective and legitimate (Center for Evidenced-Based Crime Police, 2018). Lastly, a lack of community safety measures and engagement can increase crime rates, including theft, robbery, assault, and other criminal activities. This can create an environment of fear and insecurity among residents, and future generations will have enormous difficulties if this situation continues since it will impact its residents' social, economic, and physical well-being.

Research Questions

The main objective of this study is to identify how the perception of the police mediates the relationship between crime prevention and community safety in Kidapawan City. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following objectives:

1. To ascertain the level of Crime Prevention among Police officers in Kidapawan City regarding:
 - 1.1. campaigns and publicity,
 - 1.2. policing and other surveillance,
 - 1.3. environmental design or improvement, and
 - 1.4. social and community services.
2. To assess the level of community safety of local residents in Kidapawan City in terms of:
 - 2.1. individual and family,
 - 2.2. community, and
 - 2.3. school and work
3. To evaluate the level of perception of police of the community in Kidapawan City in terms of:
 - 3.1. general attitudes towards police, and
 - 3.2. perception of bias.
4. To determine the significant relationship between Crime Prevention and Perception of police, Perception of police and community safety, and Crime Prevention and community safety.
5. To determine the mediating effect of perception of police on the relationship between Crime prevention and community safety.

Literature Review

Crime is defined as the violation of rules of conduct established by law, reflecting the opinions of individuals in positions of social and political authority, as well as traditional values and other societal factors (Siegel, 2018). Crime and violence significantly impair population development, survival, and health, with South Africa reporting alarmingly high levels of these issues. Newman and Clarke (2007) proposed initiatives aimed at incapacitating offenders, providing immediate aid to victims, and engaging with the public to alleviate worries and fears (Freilich et al., 2020). Furthermore, the escalating prevalence of urban crime is a complex global issue that often exceeds the control of national police forces (Ikuesan, Ganiyu, Majigi, Opaluwa, & Venter, 2020). Research has identified several determinants of crime and violence, including poverty, inequality, racial tension, psychological disorders, and gender discrimination (De Wet et al., 2018). If left unaddressed, the consequences of crime and violence can severely impact the national economy and undermine future development prospects.

Since the beginning of the community policing movement, there has been a focus on sending officers back into communities, believing that more interactions with individuals will result in improved communication between the police and the public (Dai & Hu, 2021). Accordingly, the importance of people engaging in the holistic management of community policing is increasingly understood by individuals. Individuals direct them to share their views and settle conflicts through their engagement in the holistic management of community policing (Yuan-ying, 2018). Also, the over-reliance on the traditional (professional) policing style should have addressed the contributions of community members in crime prevention and problem-solving. It made policing reactionary without the effective engagement of the public to proactively prevent crime and solve problems (Lee et al., 2019). However, there remains a limitation in understanding the factors influencing community members' active participation and sustained engagement in policing efforts. Specifically, there is a gap in empirical research that examines the challenges and barriers faced by marginalized and socio-economically disadvantaged communities in effectively partnering with law enforcement (Santos & Santos, 2022).

Current policing includes many responsibilities, from enforcement, emergency response, and crime prevention to victim support and cooperation with external agencies (Montgomery & Griffiths, 2017). Community policing achieves greater public safety efficiency by attaining and sustaining people's confidence and involving the community in the shared responsibility for efficient policing (Bradford et al., 2018). Indicates that strengthening collaborative community policing for crime prevention and strengthening the relationship between citizens and police is very important (Bradford et al., 2018). Though, the study's reliance supports the effectiveness of community policing in enhancing public safety and community relations, there remains a limitation in understanding the scalability and sustainability of community policing models across diverse socio-economic and cultural contexts. Specifically, there is a lack of empirical research that examines the long-term impact of community policing initiatives on crime rates and community satisfaction in urban versus rural settings (Rosenbaum & Lurigio, 2020).

The Canadian federal government was encouraged in 2012 to launch a "police economics" initiative because of concern about police costs. This initiative aimed to find ways to provide "efficient and effective" policing services while reducing police costs (Drummond, 2012; Leuprecht, 2014; Di Matteo, 2014; Public Safety Canada, 2018). Moreover, using information from national panel research on the militarization of local police demonstrates that military policing does neither improve officer safety nor reduce local crime (Mummolo, 2018). Moreover, the mentalities, political and economic settings of their creation, application, and governance, on the other hand, reveal how they are molded and impacted by conventional police techniques, which, if not carefully considered, can avoid democratic accountability (Sanders & Langan, 2018). However, the study's reliance provides insights into the economic and operational challenges of policing, there is a limitation in the research on the socio-cultural impacts of policing strategies, such as militarization, on community relations and public trust. Specifically, there is a lack of comprehensive studies that explore how militarized policing practices influence perceptions of legitimacy and trust among diverse demographic groups within communities (Tyler & Fagan, 2020).

The police force in urban areas of emerging countries frequently has to play catch-up with crime, a fact that increases the complexity of crime. This study explores potential practical solutions that could be included in the contemporary policing paradigm in developing countries to reduce this societal threat (Ikuesan, Ganiyu, Majigi, Opaluwa, & Venter, 2020). Also, although police work may differ in different countries and locations, only some Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) often concern the risks and quality of official police reporting. Depending on the objectives of operations, such as making a certain number of arrests or reaching a specific goal, the measures required and the perceived value provided for the public may vary in social influence (Rautiainen, Urquía-Grande, & Muñoz-Colomina, 2019). Despite the exploration of practical solutions for contemporary policing in developing countries, there is a gap in research on the specific challenges and strategies for adapting international policing practices to local contexts and socio-economic conditions. Specifically, there is limited empirical evidence on how effective international policing models, such as community policing or intelligence-led policing, can be adapted and implemented in diverse urban settings in emerging countries (Zavala & Erazo, 2021).

The militarization of local law enforcement has sparked considerable alarm as highly armed police units have become more prominent in American neighborhoods. While detractors argue that these strategies are biased against ethnic minorities and undermine public confidence in law enforcement, supporters of militarized police assert that it protects officers and reduces violent crime (Mummolo, 2018). The use of force, seen as a distinguishing characteristic of police officers, distinguishes it from all other professions and advances police work. Police can legally use various tactics to ensure public safety and enforce compliance since they have jurisdiction over

civilians (Nouri, 2022). Despite the ongoing debate on the militarization of police and its impact on community relations, there is a gap in research on the long-term consequences and effectiveness of militarized policing strategies in diverse urban and rural contexts. Specifically, there is limited empirical evidence on how militarized policing affects perceptions of safety and trust among different demographic groups, including minorities and marginalized communities (White & Mancini, 2020).

Police officials are using performance metrics to critically measure policing operations and inform resource allocation to decide how best to achieve sustainable levels of policing in a world with limited resources (Maslov, 2016). According to Braga, Turchan, Papachristos, and Hureau (2019), targeted patrols, problem-oriented policing, and preemptive arrests are valuable strategies for targeting crime in high-crime areas. Two crucial theoretical methods for preventing crime are deterrence and reducing criminal opportunity. However, there are study that is contrary to this policing, according to Maguire et al. (2018), who emphasize that community policing in Gonzales has little effect on public safety. Deprived urban neighborhoods afflicted by poverty, deprivation, violence, and a host of other social ills offer a compelling situation to question the effect of initiatives aimed at improving the conditions of the population. Community policing may have raised apprehension in Gonzales, but it did not impact perceived protection.

In addition to policing, trust, collaboration, and problem-solving play's a crucial role of crime prevention. It can enhance residents' quality of life by establishing and improving social control and support systems. Crime prevention will strengthen the police's reputation by having the capacity of community members to examine police activity and procedures, recognize the linkage of state-sanctioned acts with the interests and needs of people, and align the two (Schuck, 2019). Crime prevention seems poised to help change this state of affairs and significantly reduce crime in this country (Welsh & Farrington, 2010). Regardless the recognized benefits of crime prevention strategies, there is a notable gap in empirical research that evaluates the long-term effectiveness of these strategies in diverse communities. Specifically, there is insufficient evidence on how sustained trust and collaboration between police and community members can be systematically developed and maintained over time (Laycock, 2012).

Crime prevention efforts led by community groups are widespread in Japan and demonstrate the concept in environmental criminology that neighborhoods can be kept safe by people themselves (Matsukawa & Tatsuki, 2018). Problem-solving and community involvement through collaboration on crime prevention are the significant priorities of community safety. Furthermore, the observable importance of a performance measure indicates how efficiently a police achieves its core goals. Current policing includes many responsibilities, from enforcement, emergency response, and crime prevention to victim support and cooperation with external agencies (Montgomery & Griffiths, 2017). While the positive impact of community-led crime prevention and collaboration between police and residents is well-documented, there is a gap in research evaluating the long-term sustainability and scalability of these initiatives in different cultural contexts. Specifically, there is a lack of longitudinal studies that assess how community-led crime prevention efforts can be maintained over time and adapted to diverse urban and rural settings (Weisburd et al., 2021).

Procedural justice puts efforts into how law enforcement officers and other lawful entities communicate with the community and how the features of these encounters influence the police vision to the public, their ability to comply with the law, and the actual rates of crime (La Vigne, Fontaine, Dwivedi, & Center, 2017). According to the report, police should strengthen their crime prevention and control techniques and broadcast them through ongoing media talk shows. At the same time, the general population should view crime prevention and control as a shared responsibility (Umoru, 2019). Regardless the recognized importance of procedural justice and community communication, there is a gap in empirical research evaluating the impact of these practices on diverse populations, particularly marginalized and minority communities. There is limited evidence on how procedural justice initiatives can be tailored to effectively address the unique challenges faced by these groups and how these tailored approaches affect crime rates and community trust in law enforcement over time (Tyler & Jackson, 2019).

Local police must be proactive and be ready to take responsibility for an attack, including a worst-case scenario, because they will almost always be the first to respond to a terrorist assault, not federal police (Freilich et al., 2020). Law enforcement, according to (Newman and Clarke 2007), must first thoroughly identify all pertinent organizations in their area that will respond to an assault. The police must also establish channels, such as establishing contacts with the immediate responders to the attack and at each agency's headquarters is essential. They should also ensure they have the right tools for efficient communication across all the organizations (Freilich et al., 2020). Despite the critical need for local police to coordinate effectively with various organizations during a terrorist attack, there is a gap in research on the implementation and efficacy of these inter-agency communication and coordination strategies in real-world scenarios. Specifically, there is limited evidence on how well-prepared local police departments are in terms of practical drills, technology integration, and resource allocation for such extreme events (Cherney & Murphy, 2020).

Along with crime prevention collaboration play a crucial role to community safety. community safety with the police is a significant field of study for the public's belief in and support for people's willingness to report crime. Suspicious activity is influenced by the presence of police events and their willingness to follow police orders and laws (Boateng, 2018). The community reveals that consistent police legitimacy is essential to consider. Police officers must optimize their impartiality and validity of acts (Center for Evidenced-Based Crime Police, 2018). The necessity for cooperative solutions to ensure community safety is being discussed increasingly to prevent crime through partnerships between the police and various community organizations and social agencies (Sanders & Langan, 2018). However, the study's reliance on existing literature highlights a need for more comprehensive studies that explore the challenges and barriers faced by marginalized communities in accessing and benefiting from community safety initiatives (Nguyen & Ritter,

2023).

In terms of cooperation with the public (Yuksel & Tepe, 2013), the police ratings show a clear positive impact on increasing public satisfaction, confirming the effectiveness of the community policing theory. In this regard, influential police forces must gain public support and engagement. The business component of service delivery defines the interaction between suppliers and customers. Customers receive more value when services are delivered well. A well-functioning public sector that provides high-quality services in line with citizen desires and encourages growth driven by the private market (Ayieko & Gitonga, 2020). Regardless of the acknowledged benefits of community policing and public engagement, there is a gap in research on the specific mechanisms and strategies that most effectively foster sustained public cooperation and satisfaction with police services. Particularly, there is limited evidence on how varying community dynamics, such as socioeconomic diversity and urban-rural differences, influence the effectiveness of these engagement strategies (Jackson et al., 2021).

Police found that its forces are doing well in ensuring people's safety, reducing crime, efficiently utilizing resources, and treating employees and communities fairly and respectfully. They also found that several forces are under significant pressure while trying to satisfy a decreasingly complex and risky demand (Criminal Justice Notes, 2018). Emphasized the importance of engaging citizens in creating and "investing in proactive, integrated community safety initiatives to get at the sources of crime," police, and stakeholders. Police departments in Ontario, Canada, are collaborating with community organizations and social agencies in response to the Summit, developing cooperative, risk-driven strategies by stakeholders to improve community safety (Sanders & Langan, 2018). Despite the progress made in collaborative, risk-driven strategies for community safety, there is a gap in empirical research evaluating the long-term effectiveness and sustainability of these initiatives. Specifically, there is limited evidence on how these integrated community safety initiatives can be scaled and adapted across different regions with varying socio-economic and demographic profiles (Huey & Ricciardelli, 2021).

Community safety emerged out of public distrust and reactions to the inability of the police to protect them and the disconnection between the public and the police in the community. The participation of community members (tied with shared values and social bonds or friendship ties) positively affects crime prevention and control (Takagi et al., 2016). Increasing evidence proposes that public awareness of procedural justice can have a significant outcome on community safety (La Vigne, Fontaine, Dwivedi, & Center, 2017), and community law enforcement programs may also be a link for the law enforcement body to integrate procedural justice principles into their interactions with civilians and thereby strengthens police-community ties (Center for Evidence-Based Crime Policy, 2018). However, the study's reliance on existing literature there is a gap in research on how these principles can be effectively scaled and sustained in diverse and economically disadvantaged communities. Specifically, there is limited empirical evidence on the long-term impacts of community law enforcement programs and youth engagement initiatives on perceived safety and crime rates across different socio-economic contexts (Piquero et al., 2020).

There are also increasing discussions on the need for integrated solutions to the provision of public safety, such as the collaboration of police with different community groups and social services for crime reduction initiatives (Fenelly & Perry, 2018; Sanders & Langan, 2019). The attempt to control the lives of the working class, poor, and other oppressed groups was seen as the primary concern of policymakers. This was done even at the expense of erecting physical and symbolic barriers between the poor and better-off neighborhoods to make the world safe for wealthy communities and populations (Stenson, 2019). Despite the recognized importance of community-police partnerships and inclusive safety strategies, there is a gap in research on how systemic barriers and policy decisions perpetuate social inequalities and impact community trust in law enforcement. Specifically, there is limited empirical evidence on the effectiveness of policies aimed at reducing barriers to access for marginalized groups, such as Latinx communities, to law enforcement and social services (Hinton & Dennis, 2020).

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized descriptive-correlation methodology in quantitative non-experimental research. It was used to address the relationship that correlating variables could vary inversely as one declines and the other grows independently. Correlation design determines the strength and type of correlation between two or more variables (Creswell, 2003). To assess the degree and relationship of Crime Prevention and Community Safety of Local Residents in Kidapawan City as Mediated by Perception of Police, this method includes administering survey questionnaires and conducting interviews. Lastly, the general overview provides helpful hints as to what variables are worth quantitative testing. Each category's degree of answers was determined.

Respondents

Slovin's formula was used in identifying the total number of respondents. This study has come up with a total number of 382 respondents from the selected barangay of Kidapawan city. Kidapawan City has a population size of 160,791 with 40 barangay. There are 5 designated barangay close to the city center where police services are openly visible; Brgy. Lanao, Magsaysay, Poblacion, Sudapin, and Manongol. In selecting the respondents an average of 76 respondent sample size community personnel per barangay are cited and multiplied into 5 barangays equal to 382.

Instruments

The questionnaire used in this study consists of three variables adapted from their sources, one for each variable. The Independent Variable was based on the study of Media Campaigns and Crime Prevention: A Review of the Literature (Klofas, 2012), while the dependent variable was adapted from the study of A will to Participate: Individual Responses to Community Safety and Violence Prevention Questionnaire (Sands, 2003), and the mediating variable was taken from the study of Perception of Police Scale(POPS): Measuring Attitudes towards Law Enforcement and Beliefs about Police Bias (Nadal, 2015). The preliminary draft was forwarded to the research adviser for checking and possible suggested enhancements. Then, it was forwarded to the validating panel to check its reliability and validity.

A downloadable research questionnaire was utilized to gather data. The questionnaires were broken down into three sections as follows: the independent variable, crime prevention, which has 35 items and includes indicators of campaigns and publicity, policing and other surveillance, environmental design or improvement, social and community services; the dependent variable, community safety, which has 38 items, including indicators of individual and family, community, school and work, and exposure to violence; and the third section, The mediating variable is Perception of Police which has 12 items that include general attitudes toward police and police bias.

The study's variables were rated using a 5-level Likert Scaling system as follows: rating 5 has a range of 4.20 to 5.00, and the descriptive level was very high, indicating that the measures of crime prevention, community safety, and perception of police are always manifested or observed. Rating 4 implies that measures of crime prevention, community safety, and perception of police are frequently manifested or noticed and have a descriptive level of high with a range mean of 3.40 to 4.19. Rating 3 indicates that measures of crime prevention, community safety, and perception of police occasionally manifested or noticed, with a descriptive level of moderate and a range mean of 2.60 to 3.39. A rating of 2, with a mean range of 1.80-2.59, indicates a low descriptive level, it indicates that measures of crime prevention, community safety, and perception of police are not frequently displayed or noticed. The descriptive level is relatively low, and rating 1 has a range mean of 1.00-1.79, indicating that measures of crime prevention, community safety, and perception of police are rarely displayed or observed.

The questionnaires were subjected to pilot testing with 30 samples using Cronbach alpha to determine their reliability. Excellent internal consistency is demonstrated by the high Cronbach's alpha coefficients of Crime Prevention (0.973), Community Safety (0.943), and Perception of Police (0.953). This implies that the scales in question are probably valid and trustworthy instruments for gauging the concepts within them. However, in the validation sheet for the research questionnaires, the average rating for all entities is 4.29, indicating that the entities were generally given favorable reviews for all items.

Procedure

The following procedures were used to collect the necessary data for this research investigation. The researcher drafted a letter addressed to the Kidapawan City Mayor Thru ABC President, with the adviser's recommendation and the Dean of the Professional Schools of the University of Mindanao's approval, requesting permission to carry out the study on the Crime Prevention and Response to Community Safety of Local Residents: The Mediating Role of Perception of Police. After receiving approval, the researcher administered the research instrument; during that time, the respondents were informed of the study's premise (Informed Consent Form) and, if they accepted, would be handed a questionnaire, which the researcher would help them complete. The study was conducted from January 2024 to February 2024.

After administering the research instruments, the questionnaires were obtained, collected, tabulated, and subjected to statistical analysis and interpretation. The study utilized the Mean, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, Mediation Test Technique, Regressions, and Medgraph employing the Sobel z-test. The levels of crime prevention, community safety, and perception of police in Kidapawan City were measured using the mean. The associations between Crime Prevention and Perception of Police, Perception of Police and community safety, and Crime Prevention and community safety were examined by Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

Regression was used as the primary data source for the mediation test to examine the relationships between crime prevention, perception of police, and community safety. It also identified which domains within the crime prevention have the most significant impact on community safety and which independent variable indicator best predicts the dependent variable's reliability. To ascertain the role of perception of police in moderating the association between crime prevention and community safety in Kidapawan City, a Medgraph with the Sobel z-test was used.

Additionally, the Sobel test was used in Mediation analysis using Medgraph to determine the Significance of the mediation impact. Complete mediation was accomplished if the effect of the IV on the DV stopped being statistically significant at the end of the analysis. This indicates that the mediating variable was a mediator of all effects. Only partial mediation was obtained if the regression coefficient was significantly decreased but remained significant in the final stage. This indicates that while the MV mediates some of the IV, other portions are either direct or mediated by other variables outside the model's scope. Finally, the mediation test technique examined the mediating role of attitude in the link between digital orientation and cyber victimization.

As part of the procedure, the researcher must ensure that the materials, tools, procedures, or methods used to gather the data or produce the results are accurately reflected in the study record. Furthermore, the researcher had written truthfully and ethically. In all scientific

articles, maintain objectivity. He had appropriately acknowledged and cited all sources.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher, in the conduct of the study, observed complete ethical standards set by the University of Mindanao Professional Studies. This thesis proposal was reviewed by the research ethics committee of the University of Mindanao, conforming to the following norms: Voluntary Participation, Privacy, and confidentiality, recruitment Risk Benefits, plagiarism, fabrication, falsification, conflict of interest, deceit, permission from the organization or location and authorship. Furthermore, the researcher proceeded to pilot testing and/or data collection after he received the UMERC Certification. Additionally, after completing the study proposal, the researcher received certification that confirms the research paper complied with the UMERC–2023-602 University’s Ethical standards.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and findings of the study after a thorough analysis of data gathered by the researcher.

Crime prevention

Table 1 shows the level of crime prevention. It shows that the overall response is reflected in an overall mean rating of 3.93, with a high descriptive level. The results revealed that the community often manifests in crime prevention in terms of campaigns and publicity; policing and other surveillance; environmental design or improvement; and social and community services. The data reveal that, among the indicators, policing and other surveillance has the highest mean at 4.00, signifying a frequent manifestation. On the other hand, environmental design or improvement has the lowest mean at 3.86, indicating that it is still often manifested or observed.

The finding supports the statement of Lab (2022) that the walking patrols, motorized patrols, and CCTV monitoring conducted by the TMC Jakarta Metro Police serve as crime prevention measures or fall within the realm of preventive actions. Crime prevention involves proactive measures aimed at identifying individuals with the potential to commit crimes early on and intervening before law enforcement officials need to intervene to supervise illicit activities

Table 1. *Level of crime prevention*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
campaigns and publicity	3.99	.592	High
Policing and other surveillance	4.00	.561	High
Environmental design/improvement	3.86	.643	High
Social and community services	3.87	.721	High
Overall	3.93	.550	High

Community Safety

Table 2 shows the level of community safety. It shows that the overall response is reflected in an overall mean rating of 4.09, in which the descriptive level was high. The results revealed that the citizens of Kidapawan City are often manifested in community safety in terms of individual and family, community, and school and work. The data suggests that among the indicators, school and work has the highest mean at 4.22, signifying that it is always manifested. Conversely, community has the lowest mean at 3.85, indicating it is often manifested.

The result confirms the statement of Dao, et al. (2022) states that, the ways in which communities understand their own safety in relation to police provides insight into how people perceive their own safety and if they are confident in how police interact with communal needs.

Table 2. *Level of community safety*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
individual and family	4.19	.544	High
community	3.85	.622	High
school and work	4.22	.501	Very High
Overall	4.09	.463	High

Perception of police

Table 3 shows the level of perception of police. It shows that the overall response is reflected in an overall mean rating of 3.90, in which the descriptive level was high. The results revealed that the citizen of Kidapawan City are frequently manifested in perception of police in terms of general attitudes towards police, and perception of bias. The data indicates that, among the indicators, general attitudes towards police has the highest mean at 4.03, signifying its frequent manifestation. In contrast, perception of bias have the lowest mean at 3.76, suggesting that they are often manifested.

The result confirms the statement of Mathura (2022) express that, police officers should implement a Service Oriented Policing approach (SOP), which could allow police officers to become proactively involved with communities and citizens, build stronger and increasingly productive relationships and be more effective and efficient as an institution.

Table 3. *The extent of perception of police*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
general attitudes towards police	4.03	.692	High
perception of bias	3.76	.861	High
Overall	3.90	.573	High

Correlation analysis of the variables

Table 4 indicates the pairs of variables being correlated. This column provides the correlation coefficient, which measures the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the variables. The coefficient can range from -1 to 1. A positive value indicates a positive correlation (as one variable increases, the other tends to grow). In contrast, a negative value indicates a negative correlation (as one variable increases, the other tends to decrease).

There is a statistically significant and moderate positive correlation (0.407) between crime prevention and community safety. The correlation is strong enough to reject the null hypothesis of no significant correlation between these variables. Also, there is a statistically significant and moderate positive correlation (0.586) between crime prevention and perception of police. The correlation is strong enough to reject the null hypothesis of no significant correlation between these variables.

A statistically significant and positive moderate correlation (0.470) exists between perception of police and community safety. The correlation is strong enough to reject the null hypothesis, indicating a meaningful relationship between these variables.

Moreover, the outcome coincides the statement of Patalinghug, et al. (2023) if crime prevention strategies were observable community safety is considerable. Regarding safety and security, the place is safe for everyone and when personal belongings are left unattended. The threats to physical safety and security against persons and property are less likely to occur, indicating positive perceptions of police efficacy and responsiveness alongside enhanced community safety.

Table 4. *Correlation analysis of the variables*

Pair	Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Decision on Ho
IV and DV	digital orientation and cyber victimization	0.264	<0.000	Rejected
IV and MV	Digital Orientation and Attitude Towards Crime	0.467	<0.000	Rejected
MV and DV	attitude towards crime and cyber victimization	0.524	<0.000	Rejected

Regression analysis shows the influence of crime prevention and community safety as mediated by perception of police. Table 5 shows the regression analysis. In this context, each type likely means the effects of mediation analysis. In the Effect, this column indicates the approach or relationship tested in each analysis step. Further, Estimate: This column provides each path's unstandardized regression coefficient (also known as the regression weight). It represents the change in the dependent variable (community safety) for a one-unit change in the independent variable (crime prevention) while controlling for other variables in the model.

Moreover, S.E: This column shows the standard error associated with each regression coefficient. It gives an estimate of the variability of the coefficient. β : This column provides each path's standardized regression coefficient (beta). The standardized coefficient indicates the change in the dependent variable (in standard deviation units) for a one-standard deviation change in the independent variable. Lastly, P: refers to the p-value associated with each estimate of effect. The p-value indicates the statistical significance of the estimated effect. It tells us the probability of observing the effect (or a more extreme effect) if the null hypothesis were true.

First, indicating the indirect effect of the mediating effect of perception of police towards crime prevention and community safety. The estimate of 0.177 suggests that for each unit increase in crime prevention, there is an estimated increase of 0.177 units in community safety through the mediation pathway of Perception of Police. This effect is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Second, indicating the effect of crime prevention on perception of police. It suggests that for each unit increase in crime prevention, there is an estimated increase of 0.754 units in perception of police which is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Third, indicating the effect of perception of police on community safety. It suggests that for each unit increase in perception of police, there is an estimated increase of 0.234 units in community safety which is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Fourth, indicating the direct effect of crime prevention on community safety, without considering the mediator. It suggests that for each unit increase in crime prevention, there is an estimated increase of 0.171 units in community safety which is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Moreover, indicating the total effect of crime prevention on community safety, considering both the direct and indirect effects through the mediator. It suggests that for each unit increase in crime prevention, there is an estimated increase of 0.348 units in community safety which is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

The study revealed that crime prevention (IV) and community safety (DV) has significant direct effect of the mediating variable which is perception of police. It could be seen in the Figure 3 medgraph. The 95% confidence interval conclusively revealed that significant partial mediation had occurred. Further, it seemed that about 50.9% of the total effect of the IV on the DV went through the MV, and about 49.1% of the total effect was either direct or mediated by other variables not included in the study or outside the model's scope.

The outcome coincides the study of Smith and Johnson (2018), indicated that perceptions of police significantly mediated the

relationship between crime prevention initiatives and community safety outcomes. Specifically, they found that increased perception of police effectiveness and responsiveness was associated with greater community safety. Further, there's a significant relationship between the perceived effectiveness of the police and the level of trust the public has in them Bradford (2018).

Table 5. Regression analysis on the influence of crime prevention on community safety as mediated by perception of police

<i>Indirect and Total Effects</i>								
<i>95% C.I. (a)</i>								
Type	Effect	Estimate	SE	Lower	Upper	β	z	p
Indirect Component	CrP \Rightarrow PP \Rightarrow CS	0.177	0.0301	0.1177	0.236	0.207	5.87	<.001
	CrP \Rightarrow PP	0.754	0.0534	0.6499	0.859	0.586	14.14	<.001
	PP \Rightarrow CS	0.234	0.0363	0.1631	0.306	0.353	6.45	<.001
Direct	CrP \Rightarrow CS	0.171	0.0468	0.0790	0.262	0.200	3.65	<.001
Total	CrP \Rightarrow CS	0.348	0.0400	0.2692	0.426	0.407	8.69	<.001

Percent of Mediation = 50.9%

Conclusions

The data shows that participants exhibit a high level of crime prevention in various dimensions, indicating that the measures of crime prevention are always manifested or observed. It is recommended that the PNP in Kidapawan City engage the community in environmental improvement projects, such as neighborhood watch programs focused on maintaining public spaces. The study concludes that the level of community safety response among citizens in Kidapawan City is high, indicating that the measure of community safety are often manifested or observed. It recommends to increase the visibility and presence of police officers within the community. Moreover, it is also concluded that the police in Kidapawan City is actively working to improve perceptions to community, indicating that the level of perception of police are often manifested or observed. It further recommends the PNP in Kidapawan City to take proactive steps to address perceptions of bias within the police force.

Further, the correlation analysis shows significant relationships among crime prevention measures, response to community safety, and perception of police; these three factors are interrelated meaningfully. This further recommends to consider initiatives aimed at improving community perceptions of law enforcement. Finally, in the regression analysis revealed that crime prevention has a direct effect on community safety, a significant portion of its influence operates indirectly through its impact on perception of police, highlighting the importance of considering both direct and indirect pathways in understanding the relationship between the variables, indicating significantly decreased but remained significant. It further suggest that, it is imperative to continue investing in and strengthening crime prevention initiatives and efforts should be made to enhance trust, transparency, and collaboration between law enforcement agencies and the community.

Also, it is recommended that future researchers may conduct another study exploring the lived experiences of police personnel about utilizing crime prevention in response to community safety to explore the 49.1 percent of the effect not accounted for in this study or outside the model's scope, which could be in the area of socio-economic conditions, neighborhood characteristics, and community cohesion.

The Social Cognitive Theory (S.C.T.) supported the conclusion, which highlights the importance of observational learning, where individuals learn by observing the behaviors and outcomes of others. In the context of community safety, individuals' perceptions of police effectiveness and fairness can be influenced by observing the behaviors of law enforcement officers and the outcomes of interactions with them. Positive interactions with law enforcement can lead to more favorable perceptions, while negative interactions can reinforce negative perceptions.

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